

Workforce Diversity and Product Innovation in Nigeria Manufacturing Industry

Gunu, U. (PhD)

Department of Business Administration, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria

Email: umargunu@gmail.com

Omolekan, O. J. (PhD)

Department of Business Administration, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria

Email: o.omolekan@gmail.com

Olota, O.O.

Department of Business Administration, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria

Isiaka, A. A.

Department of Business Administration, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria

*Corresponding Email: o.omolekan@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

The diverse attributes of human resource in an organisation has proved to be the bedrock of creativity and innovation. Coincidentally, it is the source of disharmony, politicking and divergent views. Therefore, this study examines the effect of workforce diversity and product innovation in Nigeria manufacturing industry. Survey design was adopted using structured questionnaire. Respondents were selected randomly. The study focused on primary work force diversity dimensions. Cross tabulation and correlation were the analytical techniques adopted for the collated data. The findings of the study revealed that; age, gender, work experience, and educational background diversity have effect on product innovation. The study concluded that workforce diversity influence product innovation. Therefore, it was recommended among others that organisations should ensure that their team of employees comprises different age, gender and work experience to promote organisational efficiency.

Keywords: Core diversity, Competition, Demographic attributes, Product innovation, Business entity
JEL Classification: M1, M14.

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INTRODUCTION

Globalization has changed the way of doing business. The manufacturing industries in developing countries are increasingly feeling the pressure of innovation due to competition. Innovation is undoubtedly one of the means by which businesses can adapt to the demands of today's complex and ever-changing environment. The accomplishment of any organisation can be attributed to introduction of new products which usually is subjected to identification of customers' need, producing the goods and services to meet the identified needs. Thus, Chux (2010) described product innovation as an indispensable factor in any business organisation.

Diversity has been a major concern for organisational psychologists as homogeneity is practically unachievable in every facets of life. Workforce diversity sprang up principally to make the workplace heterogeneous and all inclusive in harnessing diverse opportunities. This phenomenon appears to be one of the major challenges of managing human resources in an organisation. Interestingly, the concept has attracted researchers in identifying the interrelationship between and among the components of workforce diversity (i.e. demographic characteristics and personality traits) to enhance organisational innovative abilities (Ehimare & Ogaga-Oghene, 2011).

The composition of demographic characteristics and personality traits differences in the workforce such as educational background, marital status, gender, age, social status, religion, personality, disability, sexual orientation, ethnicity and culture influence employees' efficiency (Onday, 2016). Diversity encompasses all groups, levels, and different calibres in an organization. There is need for workforce diversity to be properly managed to get the best out individual employee in fulfilling their career aspirations without hindrances due to their race, religion, gender, age, nationality and other non performance metrics. Wilson and Iles (1999) assert that a workforce that is diverse in nature has a better solution to the brainstorming tasks displayed in the incorporated behaviour compare to homogenous groups of employees and it is capable of influencing the overall organisational performance. Managers and leaders within an organization are expected to developed and implement practicable diversity policies for organisational effectiveness and innovative abilities.

Manufacturing firms in Nigeria are faced with stiff competition that is non-pricing. Hence, manufacturing firms are forced to think out of the box on how they can remain in the market for a very long time. Homogeneity of workforce has been identified as one of the issues hindering the effectiveness of Nigeria manufacturing industry to achieve the desired results because of the presence of employees of the same gender mostly males, age bracket, educational qualification and work experience.

Organizations all over the world are expected to adapt to the changing needs of the environment due to globalization, liberation and privatization which necessitate the needs for increased in different demographic characteristics and personality traits in the workplace. Gone were the days when employees of same age, educational qualification, work experience as well as gender come together to work in an organization. In our contemporary society, the ground has shifted to accommodating a more diversified employee. Hence, this study examines the effect of workforce diversity on product innovation. Thus, specifically the objective is to examine the influence of core and control dimensions of diversity on product innovation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Workforce Diversity Concept

The concept of workforce diversity has been defined by various scholars with different views based on their background, knowledge and exposure. Organisations today are embracing an increasingly views of diversity that identifies varieties of differences that affect employees responses to work, approach work, derive satisfaction from work or interact with each other to enhance performance (Daft, Kendrick, & Natalia, 2010). Presently, diversity is benefiting from high profile debates in organizations as a result of differences in employees characteristics (Armstrong & Mkamwa, 2010). Otike, Messah and Mwaleka (2010) defined the concept of diversity as a combination of individuals with different values, background, gender, and orientations come together as a group to interact, learn and contribute meaningfully to the realization of organisational goals and objectives. Workforce diversity is commonly seen as understanding, tolerating, esteeming and commemorating individual varieties as regards age, gender, ethnicity, education background, social class, mental ability, status, and spiritual beliefs. Jones and George (2011) are of the opinion that diversity is the variation among individual regarding demographic characteristics and personal attributes. Dessler (2011) asserts that diversity is the variety of demographic features that distinguish an organisational workforce inform of personal, social, education, and demographic attributes. Workforce diversity refers to heterogeneity in organizations as regards differences in education, ethnicity and demographic characteristics. Diverse workforce is simply amalgamations of individuals with diverse views, orientations, education and believes (Robbins, 2009). Workforce diversity is an essential tool that affects organisational policies and practices. Childs (2005) contended that a business that plans to be effective needs a general perspective on the workforce by guaranteeing that organisation comprises a mixture of employees of different background. The present day workforce is getting increasingly heterogeneous due to the influence of globalization (Kurtulus, 2012). The challenges of a diverse workforce in most of the 21st century business organization is on the best way to make a workplace where every individual can have a chance to play out their latent capacity and thusly go after advancement and other prize dependent on merit. Hence, Cascio (2010) described workforce diversity as a comprehensive business methodology that centers predominantly on expanding efficiency, creativity and duty of the various workforces while meeting their different buyer needs. Davidson and Griffin (2006) opine that diversity definition can be classified as both broad and narrow in that while the general terms focused on the individual differences between/among people while narrowly it focused on demographic and personal attributes. Davidson and Griffin (2006) believe that the presence of diversity is felt in a group or organisations that comprises of more than one personal and educational attributes.

Diversity should not be seen as hindrances or impediment to predetermined goals and objectives of the organisation but encompasses the uniformity and heterogeneity of different individual working together in an organisation with the purpose of accomplishing a common goal. Workforce diversity emanated from the lawfully secured human qualities of physical differences, gender, age, cultural, and educational differences

(Jayne & Dipboye, 2004). According to Gupta (2013) the main goal of adopting workforce diversity is to enhance better organisational decisions, productivity, innovative abilities, competitive advantages, and overall organisational efficiency.

Dimension of Workforce Diversity

Davidson and Griffin (2006) identified two levels of diversity namely: primary dimensions and secondary dimensions. First-level dimensions which is also called core dimensions comprises of characteristics which have effect on individual lives such as demographic, mental, ethnicity, physical abilities, and personal attributes. These attributes are obvious and practical impossible to alter by an individual.

Second-level dimensions or secondary dimensions are characteristics that are not obvious and vary in its effect on individual lives. They are controllable depending on individual choices in terms of acquisition, adjustment, re-modification and outright dismissal of such attributes. Second-level dimension comprises of the way and manner individual talk, religious beliefs, the environment they leave, birth tongue, education, family status, level of income, social status, job related experience, career, and organisational exposure. Though, few of these secondary dimensions attributes such as first language, religious believes, and status of the family have a powerful effect on live of individuals in an organisation.

Product Innovation

Innovation is a concept that has been widely acknowledged to assume a key role in the competitiveness of firms and countries across the globe. Innovation is acknowledged to be a major driver of improved profitability, productivity and performance. Innovation assists businesses to improve the process in which new products and services are introduced. However, product innovation can be described as creation and/or re-introduction of novel products and services or an improvement on the existing ones to deliver great value or increase the usability (Wong, 2014). The implication of this definition is that the concept of innovation is not limited to product invention but have a broader scope than mere new product. Product innovation is also seen as an act of improving the quality and the usability of existing product in meeting customers' expectation or needs. This might be in form of technical expectations, quality of raw materials, usability, functions and features of the product or services (Peter, 2014). Product innovation is significantly useful if businesses are to remain competitive and relevant. There are various theories that have been developed to underpin the relationship between product innovation and organizational performance.

According to Kulkarni (2009), he propounded the product life cycle theory, where he emphasized that product goes through five stages. He noted that at certain points if products were not modified, it becomes obsolete and unessential in the market. This necessitates the needs for organizations to invest on research and development to identified and produce goods and services to meet the ever changing consumer needs. Product is like human being that has a life cycle of stages to complete from invention to decline. Each stages of the product life are unique and require special attention to maximize the fortunate attributed to each stage. The attention and strategies adopted in each stage of the product life cycle determine the length the product stays at each stage.

(Kulkarni, 2009). In the event that products are not supported through continuous improvements, it will decline and kick the bucket normally like any human being. This explains the essentials of continuous product innovation as sustainable strategy in an organisation for survival and continuity (Palmer, 2000). Product life cycle theory implies that product is not immortal. It requires aggressive and good marketing strategies to push and pull through the market and survive competitively. Also, to sustain and extend the life spans of the product, adequate strategies such as product positioning, modification, and differentiation were required (Schilling & Hill, 1998). Innovative products become essential point in an organisation because through innovative products, customers derive benefits from the new features, attributes and usability (Khin, Ahmad & Ramayah, 2010). However, competitive oriented organisations don't just stick to single product but invest in research and development to increase the quality and usability of their products. The trending strategies now centred on differentiated products as a result of innovation which is used in gaining competitive advantage over competitors.

Organisation is said to be innovative once it able to successfully implement creative idea (Amabile, Conti, Coon, Lazenby & Herron, 1996). Also, in the view of Khin et al. (2010) product can be borne out of innovation, the moment users get value for their money through improvement in product features, design and functions. Janssen, Stoopendaal and Putters (2015) classified innovation into novelty and newness. The whole idea of innovation is continuous improvement in the idea, process, and usability of product to satisfy customers' needs reasonably.

Theoretical Review

Blau's Theory of Heterogeneity

Heterogeneity theory propounded by Blau (1977) is of the opinion that organisation that comprises of different cultural background experience different outcomes. Organisation with diverse culture and similar groups promote good rapport between/among individuals which increases the in-groups connections, shared values, and perceptions. This connection enhances group unity, cooperation, and understanding which is capable of improving organisational results. As indicated by Blau, (1977), several organisational units and functional departments at times faced with different forms of diversity but the introduction of diverse kinds of individuals with different backgrounds, culture, beliefs, ethnic, and demographic attributes create a sense of mixture of workforce to drive organisational goals and objectives. In any case, the entry of diverse employees into an organisation does not imply that all organisational groups will assemble in a diverse way. Blau believes that similarities in one factor (e.g. race) will promote social affiliations. Again, he upholds that individuals will relate with members of other groups outside their circle. Gitonga, Kamaara and Orwa (2016) also adopted this theory in their study that focused on the influence of workforce diversity on the telecom performance.

Hence, the theory reviewed above was adopted for this study; Blau's theory of heterogeneity was adopted because the theory explains that as the differences in the composition of workforce increases, the workforce brings in more diverse ideas to the organization which will result in a progressive outcome for the organization. The

assertion above is in tandem with the focus of this study which is to examine the effect workforce diversity will have on product innovation.

Empirical Review

Ozgen, Nijkamp and Poot (2011) assessed the influence of cultural diversity on innovation with particular reference to Dutch firm-level Data. The study analysed the link between employee and employer micro-data set. Firms in hospitality sectors and low-skilled migrants employers firms were expunge from the study to achieve the study's objectives. The findings revealed that aliens who form the larger percentage of employees under consideration are less innovative. Nevertheless, the study revealed a high product innovation from organisations that engages foreigners and diverse workforce.

Yang and Konrad (2011) examined the relationship among work place diversity and employee involvement on organizational innovation using selected Canadian firms as case study. The findings revealed a significant interaction among racio-ethnic, employee involvement and innovation. Besides, the study concluded that firms with high level of employees involvement promotes innovation.

Mushtaq, Haider and Khan (2015) evaluated workforce diversity on innovation in selected Pakistan telecom sector. Variables of the study were age, gender and educational background. Structured questionnaire was used to elicit information from the respondents from the two sampled firms. The study revealed that educational background and gender significantly influence employees' performance of the selected samples while recommending workforce diversity as a strategy to enhance employees' performance.

Ostojic, Mihic, Umihanic and Fazlovic (2015) investigated the effect of organizational innovation on firms' business excellence. Croatian methodology innovation scores were adopted to measure the events undertaken to develop innovation capacity while the study adopts innovation enterprise level. The composite innovation and business excellence metrics were measured. Multiple regressions were used to analyse and predict the relationship between firms' innovation and business excellence. Findings of the study revealed that managers of organisations should strengthen their innovation capacity to and improve business excellence.

METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted for this study is cross sectional to evaluate the effect of workforce demographic and personal diversity on product innovation in Nigeria manufacturing industry with particular reference to Nigeria Bottling Company, Seven up bottling company and Dogan's sugar limited, Lagos State. The organisations are in the food and beverages sectors of the manufacturing industry. The variables of the study covers core and control dimensions of diversity. The technique of samples selection is simple random sampling. The population of the study is three thousand five hundred and five (3, 505) employees of the selected companies with a sample of three hundred and sixty (360) were drawn from the population using Guilford and Flusher (1973) formulae for estimating samples. The correctly filled and returned questionnaire was three hundred and fifty-one (351). Data was collected for the study using primary source with

the use of validated questionnaire with reliability Cronbach alpha of 0.79 in Likert-scale of 5points. The data obtained by means of questionnaires were analysed using cross tabulation and correlation with the aid of SPSS.

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The core and control dimensions of workforce diversity were cross tabulated against product innovation. The hypothesis formulated from the objective is stated as:

Ho₁: core and control dimensions of workforce do not have significance effect on product innovation.

Table 1: Cross Tabulation

Gender * Product innovation

			Product Innovation					TOTAL	
			SD	D	U	A	SA		
Gender	Male	Count	56	32	40	33	47	208	Pearson X ² = 26.471 ^a Pearson R = .187 Spearman R= .187 Sig. = .000
		Expected count	46.2	32.0	29.0	45.0	55.7	208.0	
	Female	Count	22	22	9	43	47	143	
		Expected count	31.8	22.0	20.0	31.0	38.3	143.0	
Total		Count	78	54	49	76	94	351	
		Expected count	78.0	54.0	49.0	76.0	94.0	351.0	

Age * Product Innovation

			Product Innovation					TOTAL	
			SD	D	U	A	SA		
Age	18 - 25yrs	Count	21	21	19	32	9	102	Pearson X ² = 37.614 ^a Pearson R = .156 Spearman R= .190 Sig. = .000
		Expected count	14.8	21.5	14.5	27.3	23.8	102.0	
	26 - 35yrs	Count	25	35	26	44	46	176	
		Expected count	25.6	37.1	25.1	47.1	41.1	176.0	
	36-45yrs	Count	4	11	5	17	24	61	
		Expected count	8.9	12.9	8.7	16.3	14.3	61.0	
	42yrs>	Count	1	7	0	1	3	12	
		Expected count	1.7	2.5	1.7	3.2	2.8	12.0	
Total		Count	51	74	50	94	82	351	
		Expected count	51.0	74.0	50.0	94.0	82.0	351.0	

Educational Qualification * Product Innovation									
		Product Innovation							
		SD	D	U	A	SA	TOTAL		
Educational Qualification	WAEC	Count Expected count	0 6.3	0 6.2	0 4.3	9 6.2	21 7.0	30 30.0	Pearson X ² = 123.833 ^a Pearson R = -.316 Spearman R = -.271 Sig. = .000
	OND	Count Expected count	0 7.8	8 7.6	10 5.3	8 7.7	11 8.6	37 37.0	
	BSC	Count Expected count	9 12.6	29 12.3	10 8.5	8 12.5	4 14.0	60 60.0	
	MBA	Count Expected count	30 29.9	30 29.1	16 20.2	30 29.5	36 33.2	142 142.0	
	PHD	Count Expected count	35 17.3	5 16.8	14 11.7	18 17.1	10 19.2	82 82.0	
Total	Count Expected count	74 74.0	72 72.0	50 50.0	73 73.0	82 82.0	351 351.0		
Work experience * Product Innovation									
		Product Innovation							
		SD	D	U	A	SA	TOTAL		
Work Experience	1-5yrs	Count Expected count	24 14.3	21 13.9	0 9.7	14 14.1	9 15.9	68 68.0	Pearson X ² = 78.079 ^a Pearson R = .314 Spearman R = .324 Sig. = .000
	6-10yrs	Count Expected count	8 11.2	18 10.9	13 7.5	13 11.0	1 12.4	53 53.0	
	11-15yrs	Count Expected count	31 25.7	24 25.0	21 17.4	13 25.4	33 28.5	122 122.0	
	16yrs>	Count Expected count	11 22.8	9 22.2	16 15.4	33 22.5	39 25.2	108 108.0	
Total	Count Expected count	74 74.0	72 72.0	50 50.0	73 73.0	82 82.0	351 351.0		

Source: SPSS Printout, 2021

The cross tabulation shows the association between/among the variables of the study based on respondents' responses on gender and product innovation. The responses distribution based on the respondents shows that male respondents were more innovative than female respondents. Based on the trend of responses, it can be deduced that men in their nature are narrow minded, focused with high precision rate, and determined which some of the expected attributes for production optimality are in the manufacturing industry.

There is significant association between gender and employee innovations with Pearson chi square of 26.471^a, positive correlation of 18.7%, spearman correlation of 18.7%, and p-value of 0.000 which is less than the threshold of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$). With these findings, it is suffice to say that significant association and positive correlation exist between gender and product innovation.

The association between age and product innovation was significant with chi square of 37.614, positive Pearson correlation of 15.6%, spearman correlation of 19%, and p-value of 0.000. The analysis revealed that the age group of 26 – 35years seems to be more creative in the organisation than any other age group mainly because they are at their productive age. Though, this does not mean other age groups are not relevant but the presence and mixture of different age groups create avenue for cross-fertilization of ideas. Based on these findings, positive correlation exists between age diversity and creative ability of employee.

However, the result implies that employees perform well when they are part of the decision-making process irrespective of age differences and hence improving managerial innovation. Also, employees are also given equal opportunities irrespective of their gender. Diverse gender in a work team can also help to advance the contribution of different viewpoints and ideas among employees of different gender which leads to product innovation. This finding support the study of Pitt-Catsouphe, Mirvis and Berzin (2013) that affirm that age-diverse workforce are innovative and that of Hayashi, Vermeulen and Knoben (2016) on gender diversity and innovation.

Education plays significant role in influencing the level of reasoning, employees' creative ability and product innovation. Workforce with diverse educational background works together in unity and harmonizes views towards organisational goals and development. The association between education diversity and product innovation is supported by the chi-square of 123.833, negative correlation and spearman correlation of -31.6% and -27.1% respectively with p-value less than the threshold. Though, there is clear association between education and product innovation, but inverse relationship exist using Pearson and spearman correlation.

Experiences are needed to foster changes in the organisation. Likewise, the concept of brainstorming is applicable where people with diverse work experience with different background and views work together to achieve a new target or goal. Also, the length of time an individual stay on a particular work enhances their innovative ability. The findings revealed an association between work experience diversity and product innovation with chi-square of 78.079, positive correlation of 31.4% and 32.4% for Pearson and spearman correlation respectively with p-value less than 0.05. Thus, work experience influence product innovation in the sampled area.

In order words, individual with different educational background working together as a team are more innovative with creative problem solving abilities. Also, experienced employees that are more aware of the organization and its operational environment often take decisive decisions and manage issues reasonably in achieving the pre-

determined goals. The composition workforce with different educational background and those with diverse experiences can influence organizational capability to innovate new products. The result of Mushtaq, Haider and Khan (2015) which supported this study emphasized the significance of educational background on employee performance.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Findings from the study revealed that employees are given equal opportunities irrespective of their gender differences. Diverse gender in a work group can also help to foster the contribution of different viewpoints and ideas among employees of different gender which leads to product innovation. Also, the study found out that employees perform well whenever they are part of the decision-making process irrespective of their age and gender differences; hence improving product innovation. The study also found out that educational background and work related experience diversity have effect on product innovation. This implies that education plays key role in problem identification, opportunity recognition, and problem solving abilities. Besides, experienced employees that are more aware of the organization and its operational environment are able to recognise and manage risks relating to business operations more effectively. Also, the blend of employees drawn from various educational background and those with different experiences can influence organizational capability to innovate new products.

It is therefore recommended that, to guarantee that innovative products capable of attracting customers' attention are manufactured; organisations should ensure that their team of employees consist of various age groups and different gender for cross-examination of ideas. This is because younger and newly recruited employees are more skilled and energetic when it comes to handling equipment whereas the older employees are also known to have more interpersonal skills and traditional business skills. More so, manufacturing industries should continue to provide equal employment opportunities for all genders in order to encourage gender diversity. Secondly, core diversity variables such as age, gender, education and experience should form part of the basis for recruitment process to harness the benefit of workforce diversity in enhancing product innovation. Also, human capital development should be a priority to the management of manufacturing companies to train, re-train, and develop their employees for production efficiency. Management can introduce study leave as well as financial aid for the employees to further their education in order to improve organisational performance.

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